

Assessment of Damages – COVID-19

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Forewords

In the previous Paper, it was about the area of intelligence in disasters such as the Pandemic COVID-19.

That Paper It is now complemented in just in the case or Intel did not worked and the disaster could not be avoided.

Introduction

An adverse event can be defined as the phenomenon that produces unfavourable changes in people, the economy, social systems or the environment; It can be of natural origin, generated by human activity or of mixed origin and can cause an emergency or disaster.

In an emergency, response actions can be managed with locally available resources; instead, a disaster exceeds the response capacity of the affected community.

For damage of any magnitude to occur, the threat and vulnerability need to interact in a given context, which sets up the risk that damage will actually occur at a certain level of impact.

Threat is defined as the external risk factor, represented by the possibility of an adverse event or phenomenon occurring that could cause harm to people or their environment, derived from nature, human activity or a combination of both, and that it can manifest itself at a specific time and place with a certain magnitude.

I

General considerations

Threats are classified, according to their origin, into three categories.

1- Threats of natural origin.

Most of the threats fall into this category and are the ones that generally cause damage of great magnitude and intensity. Among others, we have earthquakes, tidal waves, volcanic eruptions, hurricanes, tornadoes and spontaneous landslides, which do not require human activity to occur.

2- Threats derived from human activity.

They are those related to development, urbanization, environmental and resource management activities. This category includes traffic, air and water accidents, the collapse of civil works, the spill of chemical substances, wars, environmental pollution, fires, explosions, etc.

3- Threats derived from the interaction of human activity and nature.

They are caused by abuse and neglect of human action in relation to the environment, for example, landslides, droughts and floods.

Vulnerability is defined as the intrinsic susceptibility or predisposition of an element or system to be seriously affected. It is the internal risk factor, because this situation depends on human activity.

Vulnerability is not general, but must be understood according to each type of threat. For example, a house or any other type of construction may be vulnerable to earthquakes if it is not properly designed, or it may be vulnerable to landslides if its location is inappropriate, etc.

The interaction of the threat and vulnerability at a certain moment and circumstance generates a risk, that is, the probability of generating damage due to the presentation of the expected phenomenon, in a specific place and with a certain magnitude.

Risk (threat. Vulnerability)

Risk is a calculated probability of generating damage, the factors of which intervene to varying degrees and which can be estimated if the characteristics of the threat (the magnitude of presentation) and the characteristics of vulnerability (infrastructure, social, economic, leadership, etc.), so it could be managed according to the interests of the community.

There is an acceptable risk, which implies that the community knows the damage that the presentation of this or that expected phenomenon can generate and prepares for the response when it occurs. This acceptance of risk is related to the cost-benefit or cost-opportunity analysis that has been carried out.

However, there is a risk of disaster, which implies that the damages that occur may exceed the community's possibilities to take care of them and assume them, since they would demand a superior response to the resources and would alter their development significantly.

II

Disaster management

Disaster management foresees how to best deal with the impact of disasters and their effects; It also includes the execution of those actions necessary for a timely response, such as caring for those affected, evacuation, and reducing property losses.

Disaster management has three components, namely:

1- Preparation

It is the set of measures and actions aimed at minimizing the loss of human life and other damages. It includes activities such as the elaboration of plans for the search, rescue, relief and assistance of victims, as well as the development of contingency plans or procedures according to the nature of the risk and its degree of affectation.

2- Alert

It is the state generated by the formal declaration of the near or imminent presentation of a disaster. Not only is the proximity of the disaster disclosed, but the actions to be taken by both the institutions and the population are determined. u Answer. It includes the actions carried out in the face of an adverse event and which are intended to save lives, reduce human suffering and reduce losses on property. Some examples of typical activities of this stage are the search and rescue of affected people, medical assistance, damage assessment, temporary accommodation and the provision of clothing and food.

3- Recovery

At this stage, the measures that initiate the process of re-establishing living conditions are installed.

III

Common effects of adverse health events

1- Positive social reactions.

A spirit of collaboration and mutual support is generated in the community. u Increase of communicable diseases in relation to the previous conditions.

Communicable diseases increase if environmental health conditions deteriorate and if they already existed in the community before the adverse event occurred. u Impact on individual and collective mental health.

After an adverse situation, there is always a negative impact on individual and collective mental health. Preparedness and response plans are often geared toward dealing with physical harm rather than mental health.

2- Imbalance between the supply of services and the demand generated by the event.

The blockage of the vital routes and lines generates the loss or the decrease of the hospital functional capacity, due to the decrease of public services or due to loss of access to the institution. Adverse events demand damage control and attention actions, for which additional resources and services are required to those normally available.

3- Destruction of local health infrastructure, including hospitals, resulting in the inability to respond to the emergency and the alteration of routine service provision, which could increase mortality and morbidity in the medium and long term.

4- Effects on the environment and increased potential risk of environmental hazards.

5- Commitment to the psychological and social behaviour of the communities.

6- Food shortage with nutritional consequences.

7- Spontaneous or organized displacements of the population to areas where health services cannot reach. The displacement of large groups may carry the epidemiological risk of transition from one community to another.

IV

Assessment of damages

A

Information

1. Recognize and determine the people with decision-making capacity to face the emergency in the health aspect.

2. Form and train, in advance of the emergency or disaster, a health damage assessment team for rapid assessment and for complementary assessment with responsibilities at the local, regional and central levels. This team must have safety elements to protect them from accidents.

3. Carry out a quick evaluation, in the first eight hours after the event, in coordination with other sectors. The team must report the most important damages and the main needs.

4. The complementary evaluation is carried out later, in the 72 hours after the disaster. For this, the participation of specialized technical personnel is important, since it is

required to practice technical analyzes and determine the parameters for preparing budgets for rehabilitation.

5. It is important to plan the evaluation actions. For this, the work team must take into account the corresponding supplies, such as geographic maps, threat maps, technical plans, evaluation forms, communication system, and access to portable or fixed laboratories, and local prices of materials and equipment for the estimation of rehabilitation costs, among others.

6. The adequate flow of information is very important, for which the information transmission system must be determined at the different levels. The situation room is a good instrument for gathering, processing and analyzing information to facilitate the most appropriate decision-making and the management of the corresponding resources.

7. The information necessary for the follow-up of the case must be continuous and dynamic in the following days, considering the need for subsequent evaluations to compare the progress or its absence in the care provided.

8. The evaluation of shelters represents a health priority and should be carried out as soon as possible.

B

Preliminary evaluation to take initial control measures

For the health sector, caring for those affected by a disaster is a priority. It must respond immediately to attend to victims who require emergency medical, surgical or both, depending on the type of event presented.

The first aid always comes from local resources, while regional, national or international aid is mobilized if necessary and requested by those who evaluate and make decisions.

The assessment should be implemented as soon as possible and damage levels should be determined in the areas of:

- 1- Health status of individuals
- 2-Status of health services
- 3- Life lines or basic community services
- 4- Housing

To do this, we use a standard instrument that allows the degree of damage by area to be determined very quickly, fundamentally those that affect people's health directly or indirectly, either in the short or medium term.

Therefore, in the health area, the direct and immediate damages caused must be reported: number of deaths, number of injuries and their qualification by diagnosis and severity, considering the probability of evacuation if necessary, as well as the number of disappeared and the number of victims or affected of the population. The involvement of health workers should be considered as specific data or information.

References

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